

Directors as Ethical Leaders in Digital Education

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Abstract

The digital transformation of schools brings to the fore critical ethical issues, which educational leadership is called upon to manage. This study explores the perceptions of teachers and principals of Primary Education (PE) and Secondary Education (DE) in Greece regarding the ethical dimension of leadership in the context of the digital transition of schools. A mixed methodological approach is followed, with quantitative research on 1359 teachers and qualitative research through interviews with 20 principals. The findings are organised into three main themes: equality, participation and digital responsibility; digital ethics and data protection; digital ethics policies. The quantitative results show that leadership is taking a positive stance on digital justice and accountability, while providing protection for the privacy of school community members. The qualitative research confirms the above findings and further highlights the moral concern about phenomena such as digital exclusion, students' overexposure to technology and the threat of the depersonalization of learning. Especially in the field of digital ethics policies, there is a positive intention but insufficient institutionalization. Directors act as moral guides, but they need support to shape more coherent and sustainable policies. The study proposes the strengthening of training, the development of regulatory frameworks and the systematic adaptation of school policies to the new technological conditions. Ethical leadership and digital reform cannot evolve independently. They need to coexist in a pedagogically and socially responsible framework.

Keywords: *Educational leadership, digital transformation, ethical issues, education 4.0.*

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Introduction

The digital age brings major changes in the way we perceive education and the operation of schools. Technologies are dynamically invading the educational process. This is not only about tools and platforms, but also about how students and teachers relate to knowledge and to each other. Digital transformation is not a technical change. It is a broader change that affects relationships, processes, and values. The digital

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transformation involves new forms of teaching, new skills requirements and different ways of accessing knowledge. These changes affect all stakeholders in education and bring to the surface ethical questions that did not exist in the past or that are now gaining new intensity.

The use of artificial intelligence, the continuous digitisation of personal data and the increasing dependence on digital media raise concerns about privacy, equity and transparency. Students with fewer resources often do not have equal opportunities to participate in digital learning environments (UNESCO, 2021). In addition, the fact that much of communication and assessment is transferred to digital media raises concerns about whether technology replaces human contact and authentic learning. In this new field, ethical leadership is needed more than ever.

The concept of leadership in education includes the ability to guide, inspire, and organize school life. When change is complex and questions are ethical, leadership must be based on values. Moral leadership is not limited to good intentions. It requires awareness of the consequences of decisions, the ability to empathize, and the willingness to act as a role model for the leader (Duignan, 2014).

In the context of the digital transition, the manager does not just manage infrastructure or platforms. It needs to judge which technology is pedagogically appropriate. It must ensure that all pupils have equal access opportunities. It must take care to protect the privacy of students and teachers, take breaches seriously, and create a climate of trust (Kamran, 2025). His attitude towards new technologies affects the entire school community. Teachers, especially those with reservations or limited digital skills, need a leader who inspires safety and strengthens collaboration.

The literature demonstrates that ethical leadership is based on five principles: integrity, transparency, fairness, responsibility, and care (Hrestic, Popescu & Panagoreţ, 2015). These principles acquire special significance when applied to environments affected by technology. For example, transparency is crucial in any decision concerning the processing of personal data. Justice is related to the distribution of technological resources. Care is linked to the preservation of the human dimension of learning. The headmaster who embodies these values in practice shapes schools where technology acts as a reinforcement of pedagogy rather than as a threat to the fundamental principles of education. At the same time, it promotes equal access and the democratic functioning of education for students.

Equality in education is a long-standing goal. In the digital age, it takes on new dimensions. It is no longer enough for all students to have access to the classroom. They must also have constant access to digital tools, educational platforms, the internet. The lack of these conditions leads to a new type of educational exclusion, the digital divide (European Commission, 2020). The director must recognize this and take initiatives to limit it.

Inclusive leadership is not limited to equipment distribution. It means that the school recognizes inequalities and designs actions that give real opportunities for participation. It also means that technologies are integrated into the daily life of the school in an understandable, equitable and stigma-free way. This responsibility does not belong solely to the state or technology companies. It also belongs to school leadership that acts as a mediator between innovation and social reality (Young & Arnold, 2020).

Equality is also linked to training. Teachers don't all start from the same point. They need support to understand the capabilities and limitations of digital tools. They need time to experiment. A manager who recognizes these needs creates conditions for equal development. At the same time, leadership also means taking care of the student who does not have the means at home. For the student who finds it difficult to adapt to the new learning environments. Empathy and justice acquire a very practical content when they become a political act within the school.

In summary, educational leadership in the digital age cannot be neutral or technocratic. It must be ethical, democratic and oriented to the needs of the community. It is not enough for the manager to know how the platforms work. It must reflect on how these change pedagogy, society and the role of the school. Ethical leadership is what puts people at the center of the digital transition.

The purpose of this research study is to investigate the perceptions of Teachers and Directors of Primary and Secondary Education on leadership and the ethical issues arising from the digital transformation of school units

The research questions posed based on the purpose of the research are:

1. What are the views of Primary and Secondary Education teachers on the ethical dimension of leadership in digital transformation?
2. How do principals deal with the ethical dilemmas arising from digital developments in education?

Materials and Methods

Structure of the Research Tool

The present research was carried out in the context of the preparation of the doctoral thesis. The research includes two phases: a) A quantitative one, using a two-part self-report questionnaire (Demographic-Professional Characteristics and the Leadership and Ethical Issues Section). The Section on Leadership and Ethical Issues contains 35 closed-ended questions and respondents were asked to answer on a six-point Likert scale (1=Strongly disagree, 2=Disagree a lot, 3=Disagree a little, 4=Agree a little, 5=Agree a lot, 6=Agree completely). The data collection for the quantitative research took place in the period February-March 2025. b) A qualitative phase using a semi-structured interview with two key questions during the period mid-April to mid-May 2025. The Zoom video conferencing platform was used for the interviews.

Sample Research

For the conduct of the quantitative research, the method of random sampling was used. The questionnaire was created through Google Form and sent to the Directorates of school units (Primary, Junior High and High Schools) from all over Greece via email. The sample of the survey consisted of 1359 teachers of Primary Education (PE) and Secondary Education (DE) who responded and completed the questionnaire. For the qualitative research, the method of intended sampling of Directors from all over Greece was used. The sample of the survey consisted of a total of 20 Directors of Primary, Junior High and High Schools from all over Greece

Data Analysis

The present research study followed a mixed methodological approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques in a single research project. A

central element of the mixed approach is the triangulation of data, i.e. the use of multiple sources or methods in order to cross-check and verify findings. Initially, in the quantitative survey, the data obtained from 1359 Primary and Secondary Education teachers from all over Greece were analyzed using the statistical software SPSS 29.0 for Windows.

The reliability of the internal consistency of the variables of the questionnaire (Table 1) is high ($0.958 > 0.70$). Also, the values of the correlation indicators range from $+0.743$ to $+0.911 > +0.3$ demonstrating a high internal coherence of the variables for leadership and ethical issues of the digital transformation.

A check of the normal distribution of variables was then performed with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, which showed a normal distribution (> 0.05).

The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics (Tables, Percentages, Mean Values, Standard Deviations). In the analysis of qualitative data, codes, subjects, table and diagram were created. A triangulation was then carried out to cross-reference and compare the findings from the two research phases.

Table 1. Reliability Check

	N of Items	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha
Leadership and ethical issues of digital transformation	15	0,743-0,911	0,958

Results

Quantitative Research

Regarding "Leadership and ethical issues of digital transformation", as perceived by PE and DE teachers for their school principals, the answers are analyzed based on three main dimensions (Equality, Participation and Digital Responsibility, Digital Ethics and Data Protection, Digital Ethics Policies).

a) *Equality, Participation and Digital Responsibility* The implementation of policies to combat the digital divide and promote equal access to technology is recognized by 61.4% (MT=3.83 TA=0.041). Acceptance is moderate and shows limited implementation or updating (Table 2). The promotion of technology with respect to diversity is recorded at 68.8% (MT=4.10 TA=0.041). The finding shows a positive trend and recognition of the inclusive approach. Cooperation with the local community for the development of the school is recorded at 76.6% (MT=4.34 TA=0.038). Here the perceptions are positive. Awareness of the social responsibility of technology is recorded at 73.1% (MT=4.28 TA=0.039). The evaluation reveals a substantial involvement of the director in this field. The responsible use of technology within the community is recognized by 76% (MT=4.32, TA=0.039). The agreement is satisfactory and stable. The cultivation of students' critical thinking in relation to the moral implications of technology reaches 68% (MT=4.09, TA=0.041). The attitude is positive, but without absolute unanimity.

Table 2. Percentage Distribution, Average Value and Standard Deviation, Equality, Participation and Digital Responsibility

Statements <i>The Director:</i>	I totally disagree	I disagree quite a bit	I disagree a bit	I agree a little bit	I agree quite a bit	Agree	Mean	Std.dev
1. Implements policies to reduce the digital divide and promote equal opportunities to access technology in school	8,4	14,6	15,7	24,3	20,8	16,3	3,83	0,041
2. Promotes the integration of technology in a way that respects diversity by ensuring equal participation of all students	7,7	9,3	14,1	23,8	24,5	20,5	4,10	0,041
3. Strengthens cooperation with the local community for development in the school	5,1	7,7	10,6	25,6	26,9	24,1	4,34	0,038
4. Raises awareness among students and teachers about the social responsibility of using technology	5,3	7,5	14,1	22,7	27,2	23,2	4,28	0,039
10. Implements policies that promote the responsible use of technology in the educational community	6,0	6,6	11,5	26	24,7	25,2	4,32	0,039
13. Cultivates students' critical thinking about the ethical implications of technology and artificial intelligence	7,3	10,4	14,3	22,5	24,7	20,8	4,09	0,041

b) *Digital Ethics and Data Protection*. Monitoring of the consequences of technology use in the community is recognized by 69.5% (MT=4.17, TA=0.040). Acceptance is satisfactory but not high (Table 3). The adoption of privacy measures is reflected in 75.9% (MT=4.40, TA=0.038). The trend is positive. Compliance with copyright legislation is evaluated by 82.4% (MT=4.71, TA=0.036). This is a fairly satisfactory result. The existence of protocols on legal issues is assessed by the 71.9% (MT=4.31 TA=0.039). The attitude shows confidence. Teachers' guidance on the legal consequences of online tools is assessed at 69.1% (MT=4.19, TA=0.041). The picture is positive, but there is room for improvement. The emphasis on ethical data management and technology transparency is estimated at 74.1% (MT=4.40, TA=0.038).

Table 3. Percentage Distribution, Average Value and Standard Deviation, Digital Ethics and Data Protection

Statements <i>The Director:</i>	I totally disagree	I disagree quite a bit	I disagree a bit	I agree a little bit	I agree quite a bit	Agree	Mean	Std.dev
5. Monitors the impact of the use of technology on the educational community.	6,8	8,2	15,5	21,0	28	20,5	4,17	0,040
6. Takes measures to protect the personal data and privacy of students and teachers at school	4,6	7,3	12,1	21,2	29,1	25,6	4,40	0,038

7. Complies with the legislation on copyright and use of educational material on the internet	2,9	4,6	10,2	17,9	29,8	34,7	4,71	0,036
8. Implements protocols of actions to address legal issues arising from the misuse of technology by students and teachers	3,5	10,2	14,3	20,3	26,9	24,7	4,31	0,039
9. Guides teachers on the legal implications of using online tools in the educational process	6,2	9,9	14,8	21,2	23,8	24,1	4,19	0,041
11. Emphasizes ethical data management and ensuring transparency in the use of technology in school	4,9	6,4	11,7	23,2	28,3	25,6	4,40	0,038

c) *Digital Ethics Policies*. The provision of training on digital ethics and online behaviour is recorded at 63.9% (MT=3.98 TA=0.042). The attitude is positive but slightly restrained (Table 4). The consideration of ethical dimensions when introducing new technologies is recognised by 73.8% (MT=4.29 TA=0.038). The picture shows sensitivity and attention. The adaptation of digital ethics policies to the new challenges is estimated at 65.8% (MT=4.06 TA=0.041). The agreement exists, But a part of the respondents express skepticism.

Table 4. Percentage Distribution, Average Value and Standard Deviation, Digital Ethics Policies

Statements <i>The Director:</i>	I totally disagree	I disagree quite a bit	I disagree a bit	I agree a little bit	I agree quite a bit	Agree	Mean	Std.dev
12. Provides training to teachers and students on issues of digital ethics and responsible behavior online	8,6	11,3	15,9	20,5	25,2	18,5	3,98	0,042
14. Takes into account the ethical dimensions of decisions related to the introduction of new technologies in education	5,7	6,0	14,6	23,4	28,3	22,1	4,29	0,038
15. Digital ethics and safety policies in schools are constantly adapting to new technological challenges.	7,1	11,0	16,1	21,2	24,3	20,3	4,06	0,041

Qualitative Research

From the responses to the 20 interviews, it can be seen that the principals are particularly concerned about two main categories of ethical issues: (1) the social and psychological impact of technologies on students (e.g. reduced socialization, dependence on screens, alteration of human relationships) and (2) privacy and security issues (e.g. students' digital privacy, their exposure to spam, cyberbullying). In addition, some principals mentioned as a moral concern equal access, i.e. not to leave behind students or schools that do not have the means as well as the issue of excessive "digitalization" of procedures at the expense of human contact. Almost all managers

agree that technologies are useful and unavoidable, but emphasize that they must be used with moderation and critical thinking in order to maximize benefits and minimize moral hazards. Below are the individual sub-topics that emerged from the responses (Table 5, Figure 1).

Sub-topic 1.1: Impact of technologies on students' social skills and psychosynthesis. Many managers are concerned that excessive use of digital media can have negative consequences on children's socialisation and development. "I have noticed it in my own child as well... was greatly affected. More contact with the computer, less social contacts," one manager shared personally (Syn. 1). This observation, which is also linked to the period of distance education, reflects a general concern: does technology isolate students, encouraging them to focus on screens instead of face-to-face interaction? "The social fabric here is broken. There is no neighborhood..." noted emphatically by a director (Syn. 13). This concern is essentially the anxiety that the human dimension in education will recede in the face of digital. Often, principals emphasize that technology is a tool, not an end in itself, and should not replace live teacher-student interaction or students with each other (Syn. 1, "it is a tool but cannot replace social contacts"). Also, some are concerned about mental formation: "I'm afraid that developments [e.g. ChatGPT] may evolve in such a way that... to replace the teachers," said a principal (Syn. 12). While this may seem exaggerated, it does reveal a fear that technology will depersonalize education. Overall, the moral concern for the preservation of the human dimension is recorded. Principals do not want schools to become cold digital environments where students lose contact, critical thinking (due to ready-made answers) and social learning.

Sub-topic 1.2: Personal data and privacy – digital security. One of the most frequently cited ethical issues is the protection of students' and teachers' personal data on digital platforms. "Personal data for sure" (Syn. 4), ".....personal data is an issue that concerns us all" (Syn. 9). Many people are concerned about where they are stored and who has access to student data (grades, attendance, sensitive information) when online systems are used. Also, the use of third-party applications (e.g. cloud tools) raises GDPR issues. "I am very concerned about personal data. Since our computers are rebuilt, they may have broken software," one director remarked (Syn. 16), bringing a practical dimension (old computers may not be secure). Overall, managers feel a responsibility to safeguard the privacy of their community members in the digital environment. Related is the issue of cybersecurity and content: not exposing students to inappropriate material or online threats. "Cybersecurity. The data... the school must make sure that there are some safety nets" (Syn. 19) – a phrase that encapsulates this concern. Some reported incidents: "Once we faced such issues and fortunately we solved it" (Syn. 10), without details but possibly implying a case of cyberbullying or breach. Also, especially in video conferences, there have been issues (e.g. "zoom-bombing"). Principals place importance on safety ethics: they consider it their duty to ensure that technology in school is used in a way that does not harm the privacy, safety and dignity of students (and teachers). On a practical level, many adhere to strict protocols (e.g. parental consent, updates, limited disclosure of student photos, etc.) (Syn. 3, 8, 18).

Sub-topic 1.3: Digital addiction, breach of boundaries and cyberbullying. A subcategory of concerns, linked to the above, is the risk of students becoming addicted to screens and exposing them to phenomena such as cyberbullying or the unethical use of technology in general. Some directors reported specific incidents that deeply troubled them. A principal said: "I had reached the prosecutor this year for issues, for some discussions that were shared between students, not colleagues, on the internet" (Syn. 15). This

serious statement indicates that there has probably been a case of online harassment or trafficking of inappropriate material that has taken on a legal dimension. The fact that a director had to reach out to a prosecutor underlines the profound moral and legal risk of such situations. Others spoke more generally: ".....personal data breach, issues dealing with child exploitation" (Syn. 8) as categories of issues. Also, some include in this context the logic of the burden on teachers and the addiction of students: "As far as the use by teachers is concerned, it should not be something that they feel burdens them..... a child who is already immersed in technology, we also have lessons done with the use of new technologies, although even though children are familiar, it can create a problem of addiction to the use of devices" (Syn. 11). In general, it emerges that school leadership is alert to ethical behavioral hazards. From addiction and abuse (e.g., students playing or doing inappropriate things online) to in-school bullying (such as videotapping teachers without permission, smearing online, etc.) (Syn. 15). They consider it their moral duty to set boundaries and educate students in digital ethics.

Sub-topic 1.4: Equal access and democracy. Another ethical issue that has been mentioned (although not by many, but it is important) is equality in digital education. ".....I am concerned about whether all children will have the same opportunities, the same opportunities to take advantage of them, and the school should offer this..... Otherwise, equality is not guaranteed. We also have issues of democracy." (Syn. 14). This statement brings up the issue of the "digital divide", morally the introduction of technology should not widen inequalities between schools or students. Therefore, the principals think that it is unfair for some schools to have equipment and others not, or for some students to have Internet/computer at home and others not. This parameter is of a moral nature: it concerns social justice within the educational community. On a practical level, for example, during the pandemic, they saw how unevenly distance education affected students depending on their resources. That is why some people mention it, wanting to emphasize that the digital transition must take place without leaving anyone behind. Democracy was also mentioned in the sense of the balance of power: one principal said that his role is to "mitigate" the pressure that teachers are under from above to adopt ICT. "There was some reaction that they were being pressured, on the other hand, okay I let them free to do whatever they want..", (Syn. 10), "....the use by teachers, not something that they feel burdens them" (Syn. 11), a kind of moral care for his colleagues. Overall, however, the central point is the care for the underprivileged. Leadership sees a responsibility to keep inclusion in the development and use of digital applications.

Table 5. Ethical Considerations about Use New Technologies in School

Code	Interview Excerpt
Reduce social contacts	"My child... received a lot of distance education... more in contact with the computer..... fewer social contacts" (Syn. 1)
Personal Data & Privacy	"As far as personal data is concerned..... this is always a very serious issue" (Syn. 7)
Cybersecurity & online risks	"Cybersecurity. The data... the student will use interactive – he must feel safe" (Syn. 19).
Equal access	"Of course [the State must take measures], otherwise equality is not guaranteed..." (Syn. 14)

Figure 1. Leadership and Ethical Issues

Discussion

The digital transformation of education raises new ethical issues, making the role of school leadership crucial. This module documents the quantitative and qualitative findings of a survey on leadership and ethical issues in digital transformation, organized in three themes: (a) Equality, participation and digital responsibility, (b) Digital ethics and data protection, (c) Digital ethics policies. Each sub-section relates the findings to the relevant theoretical background. It is worth noting that the importance of ethical leadership in the digital age is widely recognized – e.g., studies show that educators consider ethical leadership to be an essential ingredient for sustainable and meaningful educational reforms (Sherchan et al., 2024). The findings of our research confirm this view, presenting an overall positive picture of leadership, with some room for improvement in structured interventions.

Regarding equality, participation and digital responsibility, the majority of teachers recognize that principals actively promote digital equality and responsibility in school. In particular, around 61% of teachers agree that policies are in place to reduce the digital divide and ensure equal access to technologies. Similarly, almost 69% believe that the integration of the new tools is done with respect to diversity, ensuring that all students are actively involved. School leaders appear to be working with the local community on school development (76.6% of teachers reported this), adopting a democratic and inclusive approach. At the same time, 73% observe that leadership makes the educational community aware of the social responsibility involved in the use of technology, while about 76% state that the responsible use of digital media by students and teachers is promoted. Interestingly, ~68% of teachers believe that students are cultivating critical thinking about the ethical implications of technology – a positive sign, although it leaves room for improvement as a significant percentage do not yet see complete consensus. Qualitative data confirms these findings: principals interviewed underlined that they prioritize the equal participation of all students in the digital transformation. As they characteristically stated, they consider it their moral obligation not to be left behind due to lack of digital access or skills. They stressed that

the introduction of technology must be done in a way that does not widen existing inequalities but, on the contrary, seeks convergence. Some principals have also spoken of their democratic style: they avoid putting too much pressure on teachers to adopt new tools immediately, giving time and support to ensure that adaptation is fair for all. In addition, they expressed concerns about the human dimension of learning – they fear that the reckless use of digital media could lead to social isolation of students or undermine interpersonal communication. Characteristically, they said that "technology is a tool, not an end in itself", stressing that it should not replace the human contact between teacher and student. Instead, students need to learn to use ICT with moderation and critical competence in order to maximise benefits and minimise ethical risks. Overall, the data suggests that school leadership fosters a culture of digital inclusion and accountability.

These findings are fully consistent with the requirements of modern literature. As schools adopt new technologies, there is an urgent need for educational leadership to ensure digital equality – i.e. equal access for all students to digital media – and to bridge the digital divide between socio-economically diverse groups (European Commission, 2020b). The European Commission has recognised that the digital transformation in education must be accompanied by policies that guarantee equal access to new technologies for all, so as not to exacerbate social inequalities due to the digital divide (European Commission, 2020; UNESCO, 2020). At the same time, international organizations such as UNESCO emphasize that the digital transformation must be inclusive and human-centered, keeping education socially responsible and oriented to human values (UNESCO, 2021; UNESCO, 2023). The emphasis on principals to "leave no one behind" is in line with global recommendations: during the pandemic period, UNESCO pointed out that without targeted interventions, millions of students without a computer or internet would be stranded, undermining the principle of equal opportunities (UNESCO, 2020). The literature argues that educational leaders must actively address digital inequality by ensuring equal access to technology resources for all students (Ghavifekr & Yue, 2022). In addition, the principles of inclusive leadership indicate that leaders must recognize and value diversity, creating a climate where each individual feels accepted and able to contribute (Young & Arnold, 2020). It has been found that an inclusive approach to leadership can help schools address challenges such as increasing multiculturalism and inequalities in access to education (Young & Arnold, 2020). This is exactly what is reflected in the practices of our principals: working with the community, making democratic decisions and supporting teachers, so that innovations are introduced in a fair and acceptable way. The study by Negussie and Hirgo (2023), for example, shows that successfully implementing education policies requires leadership that inspires a shared vision and ensures the participation of all parties. The choice of many principals not to abruptly impose changes, but to encourage the active participation of teachers and students, reflects precisely this principle of participatory leadership (Negussie & Hirgo, 2023).

In addition, the results highlight the importance of digital responsibility and critical thinking in education 4.0. Principals who raise awareness in the community about the social responsibility of technology and cultivate students' critical thinking act as digital education providers. According to Green et al. (2021), education should aim to develop students' digital responsibility so that they can recognize and address the ethical issues that arise in the digital environment – such as privacy, disinformation or data protection issues. The finding that the responsible use of technology is promoted in schools reflects the concept of digital citizenship promoted by international bodies: students and teachers must develop conscious and responsible digital behaviors

(UNESCO, 2021). The emphasis of many managers on the balance between technology and human contact is also supported in the literature. Excesses in the use of digital media can lead to "digital fatigue" and alienation (UNESCO, 2023), which is why leaders need to cultivate a culture of moderation. Technology must be included as a tool that serves pedagogy, not as an end in itself that replaces human relationships, a position that reflects the values of human-centered education and has been supported in international exhibitions (UNESCO, 2021). Finally, the Greek literature confirms the importance of the ethical dimension: teachers in our country identify issues such as equality in access to technology and the protection of students' personal data as daily challenges (Anastasiou et al., 2024). The values of justice, care and social sensitivity must guide the management of technology, so that education remains humane and socially responsible (Hadjivassiliou, 2024). In summary, the findings on equality, participation, and accountability are in full agreement with the theoretical framework: today's effective leaders must be inclusive, ensure equal opportunities in digital learning, and cultivate an ethical digital culture in students (Halim et al., 2023; Green et al., 2021).

Regarding Digital Ethics and Data Protection, the quantitative results show a positive picture of school leadership. An overwhelming 75.9% of teachers find that the headteacher takes measures to protect the personal data and privacy of students and staff. Even higher – 82.4% – is the percentage of those who agree that the legislation on copyright and legal use of digital material in school is respected. In addition, nearly 70% (69.5%) recognize that leadership monitors the impact of technology on the educational community (e.g., the impact on student behavior, relationships, or performance). At similar levels (~72%) there is also the perception that protocols have been established to deal with legal issues that may arise from the misuse of technology. Around 69% state that the Principal guides the teaching staff on the legal consequences and obligations arising from digital tools (e.g. GDPR rules, copyright). Finally, 74% of teachers agree that special emphasis is placed on transparency and ethical data management in school. Overall, nearly three out of four teachers recognize that school leadership demonstrates responsibility, sensitivity, and vigilance on privacy, security, and digital ethics.

Qualitative findings complement and deepen this picture. Almost all the principals in the interviews expressed a strong sense of responsibility for the protection of personal data and digital security in the school. They said they feel responsible to safeguard the privacy of students and teachers when using digital platforms, in line with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). In fact, many are concerned about where students' data is stored and who has access to it, showing concern about GDPR compatibility issues and digital privacy in general. A particularly vivid example mentioned was the case of a serious incident of cyberbullying, where the principal had to turn to the authorities (public prosecutor) in order to protect the students. Other principals spoke about the challenge of cybersecurity as a whole – e.g. the need to protect students from inappropriate content or risks online, as well as to prevent phenomena such as "zoom-bombing" in online courses. All agreed that they consider it their duty to ensure that the use of technology in school does not harm the privacy, security or dignity of students. They outlined a number of practical measures they are taking: strict consent protocols (e.g. collection of written parental consent before using new digital applications), regular updates of staff on digital safety issues, limited publication of photos of students online, use of content filters and immediate intervention in any indication of a breach. Indicatively, in phenomena such as the "zoom-bombing" that were mentioned, the directors reacted immediately by closing

the security gaps and setting rules for video conferences. It is clear from the testimonies that privacy and ethics issues are a top priority for them.

It is noteworthy that in this topic there was a complete coincidence between quantitative and qualitative data. The numbers from the questionnaire show that the vast majority of teachers trust leadership on this issue – and the interviews explain why this trust exists. The directors specifically described how they implement in practice what the indicators indicate: strict compliance with the legislation, prompt response to incidents, constant vigilance. For example, the high rate (~82%) of compliance with copyright laws acquires content through leaders' narratives. All of them mentioned that they constantly inform teachers to use only approved material, to respect legal software licenses and to teach children the concept of copyright. Similarly, managers' reports of incidents such as cyberbullying show the severity with which they deal with threats – something that may not be fully reflected in the cold numbers. No substantial contradiction was found between the quantitative and qualitative picture. Rather, it is a case of triangulation where the two types of data reinforce each other. Teachers declare broad trust in leadership on ethical issues in the digital realm, and the personal testimonies of leaders point to examples of responsible management that justify this trust.

The image of a school leadership that prioritizes data protection, security, and ethics reflects the best practices outlined in the literature on ethical leadership in the digital age. It has been emphasized that effective educational leaders must possess knowledge and sensitivity to issues such as student privacy, cybersecurity, and digital law in order to shape a safe digital learning environment (Sharma et al., 2023; Kamran, 2025). In this context, the adoption of strict data protection protocols and the regular training of all those involved in cybersecurity issues emerge as necessary conditions for the successful digital transition of schools (Sharma et al., 2023). The practice of many principals to provide continuous information and guidance to staff on legal and ethical aspects is in line with international guidelines that encourage teachers' lifelong learning in digital skills and the ethical use of technology (OECD, 2022).

It is particularly critical for leaders to cultivate a culture of transparency and accountability in the school's digital practices. Peckham (2021) underlines that any introduction of new technology should be accompanied by clear communication to the educational community about the principles that govern it – something we have seen implemented, for example, by informing parents and teachers about the rules of using digital platforms. The institutionalization of procedures for dealing with incidents (such as protocols for cyberbullying or data breach incidents) is considered a *sine qua non* in the digital security literature (Peckham, 2021; Murphy et al., 2021). Indeed, the need for leadership that transparently anticipates and addresses such issues is now considered imperative in the age of advanced technologies (Murphy et al., 2021; Ogrzeanu et al., 2022). The preventive action practices described by our principals – such as direct incident intervention and the establishment of preventive rules – find theoretical support in the view that leadership that prioritizes the ethical use of technology creates a climate of trust in the school. According to Halim et al. (2023), when teachers have confidence in the digital environment of the school (e.g. they feel that their data is secure and that there are fair rules), then they participate more confidently in digital innovations. In other words, ethical leadership works proactively not only by preventing problems (data leaks, access inequalities), but also by encouraging teachers' participation in digital transformation (Halim et al., 2023). This observation explains why in our research the perceptions of teachers and principals

converge so much. There is a foundation of trust, which has been built through consistent ethical practices on the part of leadership. In addition, the leadership literature points out that effective leadership requires the incorporation of ethical principles at all levels of decision-making (Hrestic et al., 2015). Principals who adopt ethical criteria at every level – from school strategy to day-to-day classroom problem-solving – create a safe and trustworthy environment where students and teachers feel protected and respected (Kamran, 2025). This approach seems to characterize the participating leaders, who have established that privacy and security are non-negotiable values of school culture. It is no coincidence that the need to raise awareness among managers on these issues is also highlighted in the Greek reality. The study by Anastasiou et al. (2024) showed that there is often a divergence between the perspective of principals (who focus on administrative processes) and teachers (who experience practical issues such as technology equity and data protection). This gap is bridged when leaders acquire adequate training and sensitivity to ethical issues – which, as our findings show, leads to a positive educational environment where everyone feels safe and trusts the learning process (Kamran, 2025).

Regarding the Digital Ethics Policies, adopted (or not adopted) by school leadership – i.e. official actions, regulations and training programs around the ethical use of technology – the quantitative results, although positive, appear slightly lower compared to the previous dimensions. Only 63.9% of teachers agree that the headteacher provides systematic training to teachers and students on issues of digital ethics and responsible online behavior. This percentage, although representing a relative majority, suggests that almost 1 in 3 teachers have not found adequate such training. In other words, there is room for improvement in terms of organised training actions around digital ethics. On the other hand, a significantly higher 73.8% state that leadership takes ethical dimensions into account when introducing new technologies into education. This large majority shows strong sensitivity and attention on the part of the administration when making decisions on innovations: most teachers recognize that before adopting a new digital tool, its ethical implications are examined. Also, 65.8% agree that existing digital ethics and safety policies in schools are constantly adapting to new technological challenges. That is, about two-thirds believe that school rules and practices are evolving to keep pace with the demands of the digital age (while the remaining one-third may not see such flexibility). The overall picture here is positive but restrained. Although a significant portion of teachers recognize an effort and sensitivity of the leadership, organized training around digital ethics does not garner as high acceptance as other aspects (compared, for example, to data protection or the promotion of equality).

The qualitative findings provide an explanation for this relative lag. In the interviews, the principals did not extensively mention specific official policies or structured training programs for digital ethics in their school. While everyone more or less agreed that they see it as their duty to morally guide students in the digital environment, most admitted that this is done informally and integrated into everyday practices, rather than through some institutionalized program. For example, many said that they consider it part of their role to "educate" students digitally – setting boundaries, discussing with them about responsible behavior online, encouraging "moderation" in the use of new media. However, no one spoke about the existence of any specific training program or seminar for staff on the subject of digital ethics. Most of the leaders' references were about general principles and attitudes (e.g., "technology in moderation", "man above all") rather than organized actions. For example, one principal said: "We don't have a formal schedule, but I constantly stress to colleagues to think about the consequences

before using a new app in the classroom." One principal commented: "Students need to learn that there are rules on the internet – we say this in assemblies and daily discussions, but no, we haven't done any special seminars." From such statements, it becomes apparent that leaders embrace the need for ethical guidance in the digital world, but have not yet translated it into specific, structured policies or programs in their school. An interesting point that emerged in the interviews is the way managers think critically about the ethical implications of new technologies. Many are actively concerned about the dubious meaning of some innovations: for example, several have expressed concern that developments such as artificial intelligence (e.g., the use of ChatGPT-like tools) may negatively affect education, perhaps by substituting the human factor or encouraging copying. This concern shows that before a new technology is adopted, school leaders do reflect on its ethical dimensions and its implications for pedagogical practice – just as it was recorded in the quantitative dimension (almost 74% of teachers agree that ethical considerations are taken into account in introducing innovations). Thus, we observe a partial convergence and complementarity between the two types of data: the quantitative results indicate that the effort of leadership in this field is recognized, but not to the same extent as other dimensions; Especially in terms of training, acceptance is lower (~64%). Quality interviews seem to agree. There were not many references to formal training or specific school policies of digital ethics, which is in line with the suggestive gap that the numbers show. At the same time, however, both sources agree that directors show moral sensitivity. The high percentage (73.8%) stating that ethical considerations are taken into account in the introduction of new technologies is reflected in the narratives of the principals, which describe their concerns about technological innovations (e.g. the role of artificial intelligence in the classroom). Therefore, there is convergence in intention and perception: leaders seem to have the right attitude and awareness of ethical issues (both their numbers and their words confirm this), but there is a divergence in the degree of organized implementation. In other words, our research suggests that while managers have an ethical conscience and a personal commitment to digital ethics, this commitment has not yet been fully translated into systematic training policies and a continuous updating of digital ethics rules. This is a point of improvement highlighted by the triangulation of data. The generally positive image of the leadership is thus complemented by the suggestion of a direction for the future: the further institutionalization of digital ethics in schools through organized actions and policies.

These observations are consistent with the theoretical framework that proposes that ethical guidance in the digital age should be both a matter of personal attitude and a matter of institutional policy. The international literature has highlighted the need for school units to develop explicit policies and continuous strategic review regarding digital ethics (European Commission, 2020; OECD, 2022). The European Commission, through the Digital Education Action Plan 2021–2027, stressed that the integration of technologies in education must be accompanied by a strong digital security framework and that these strategies need to be constantly reviewed in the face of new challenges (European Commission, 2020). Accordingly, the OECD points out that education policies must constantly evolve to ensure the equitable and safe use of digital technologies in schools (OECD, 2022). This is exactly what our Policy Adaptation Index reflects: the fact that two out of three teachers see school regulations adapting to new challenges is an encouraging sign of alignment with international recommendations.

At the same time, the lack of organized training observed agrees with studies showing that many schools worldwide have not yet adequately integrated education in digital ethics into their curricula – despite its necessity (UNESCO, 2019; Green et al., 2021). Green et al. (2021) emphasize that the development of digital responsibility must become a goal of the curriculum, warning that without formal education the younger generations will not be able to manage issues of privacy, disinformation and other ethical risks of the internet. Therefore, the gap we identified in training is not unusual, but it is something that is recognized as an area to be strengthened internationally. The literature on leadership in Education 4.0 points out that leaders must incorporate ethical principles into all processes of technology introduction (Duignan, 2014; Hrestic et al., 2015). As Hrestic et al. (2015) report, effective educational leadership requires the integration of ethical principles at all levels of decision-making – which means that the ethical dimension cannot be left to good will alone, but must become a structural element of school policy. Thus, principals should ideally draw up a clear framework of principles and rules for the proper use of technology, which will guide both teachers and students (Khan, 2005). Such digital ethics policies include guidance on issues such as data protection at school, safe online browsing, responsible social media communication, and tackling abuse (Oliveira & Souza, 2021; Livingstone & Stoilova, 2021). An effective leader, according to the literature, is not content with being sensitive himself, but takes care to constantly inform and educate staff and students about these policies (Oliveira & Souza, 2021). This is in line with our observation that where there has been a deficit, it has been in the lack of formal information/training – so the recommendation is to put more emphasis there.

Another element of digital ethics policies is their dynamic adaptation. Rules should not remain stagnant, but should be revised and modernised as new technologies emerge (European Commission, 2020). For example, the introduction of AI into schools requires leaders to review existing guidelines and introduce any necessary modifications to meet the new ethical challenges (Murphy et al., 2021). Issues such as algorithm bias and transparency in automated decisions are now in the spotlight. It is noteworthy that in Greece it has been stressed that policymakers and educational leaders must ensure that the algorithms used in education do not reproduce existing biases or inequalities, maintaining equal access and fair evaluation for all students (Halvatzi, 2024). The concerns expressed by managers about ChatGPT and other AI tools are perfectly in line with these warnings: they show a proactive conscience against the dangers of rampant technology adoption. The literature argues that the emergence of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence algorithms brings new ethical challenges (such as opacity, automated decision-making issues) and makes the need for ethical leadership and transparency even more compelling (Murphy et al., 2021; Peckham, 2021). Based on this, it is stressed internationally that the digital transformation of education must be human-centric and accompanied by a strong ethical governance framework (UNESCO, 2021; OECD, 2022). A leader who prioritizes digital ethics policies creates a school environment where technology is used responsibly and values – such as transparency, respect, and security – govern every digital practice (Demartini & Benussi, 2017). In this way, a culture of trust and ethics is established in the school, which shields the educational community against the dangers of the digital world and allows its opportunities to be exploited in a socially beneficial way (Demartini & Benussi, 2017).

The theory and findings converge that the ethical aspect of educational leadership in the digital age is now non-negotiable. Leaders must act as ethical role models in the use of technology: demonstrate personal integrity and sensitivity (as they do, according

to teachers), but also establish those structures (policies, regulations, training) that will ensure that the entire school community moves safely and ethically in the digital environment (European Commission, 2020; Oliveira & Souza, 2021). Our research has shown that in practice, school leaders in Greece are largely responding to this challenge: they promote equality and responsibility, actively protect privacy, and put the ethical questions of new technologies on the table. The only element left is the further transmutation of this ethical consciousness into concrete policies and actions – a step that will further enhance trust and security in the 21st-century digital school (Sharma et al., 2023; OECD, 2022).

The comparative examination of quantitative and qualitative findings demonstrates that school leaders address the ethical issues of digital transformation with seriousness, professionalism and a willingness to collaborate. Principals have embraced the principles of digital equality and ethics, generally ensuring a fair, safe and responsible digital learning environment. This is reflected in the broad acceptance of teachers and the positive examples from everyday school practice. At the same time, it emerged that there is room for them to move to a next stage of maturity: to institutionalize and systematize their efforts on digital ethics even more, through formal policies and training programs. The international literature agrees that this will further strengthen the school's resilience to future challenges (European Commission, 2020; UNESCO, 2021). However, the overall picture is optimistic. School leaders are already largely acting as ethical leaders in the digital age – embedding the values of equality, transparency and respect in practice. With appropriate support and ongoing feedback, they can further evolve these practices, shaping schools that not only leverage technological innovations, but do so in a way that is pedagogically beneficial and socially responsible (Peckham, 2021; Demartini & Benussi, 2017). Thus, the digital transformation of education can deliver on its promises, without jeopardizing the fundamental values and rights that lie at the core of education.

Conclusion

The digital transformation in education is highlighting new ethical challenges in a strong way. Within this environment, the role of school leadership is not limited to technology management. It also needs to cover the critical field of moral guidance. The findings of the survey presented show that principals understand this responsibility and try to incorporate it into the day-to-day operation of the school.

Teachers recognise that in most schools there is a desire to ensure equal access to digital technologies. They observe that principals strive to enhance the participation of all students, regardless of social or economic barriers. Cooperation with the local community, democratic decision-making and teachers' support in this transition contribute to a gentle and fair integration of the new media. Most managers try not to turn technology into an end in itself. On the contrary, they use it as a tool, with respect to the human dimension of learning. They want students to acquire a critical attitude towards digital media and use them with moderation and responsibility. Technology should not take children away from human contact or put a psychological burden on their daily lives.

In the field of data protection and digital ethics, managers show a clear commitment. Most of them comply with the relevant legislation, inform teachers and intervene immediately in critical incidents. An example is dealing with phenomena such as cyberbullying, where managers acted decisively. They often express concern about

where students' personal data is stored or who has access to it. It seems that they don't consider security and privacy issues to be just technical. They approach them as basic elements of school life, which require constant care and sensitivity. They also adopt practical measures, such as collecting parental consent, using filters and informing staff frequently. This attitude strengthens the trust of the school community.

On the subject of digital ethics policies, the picture is positive, but less clear. Most directors recognize the importance of the ethical dimension, yet few have established specific and organized policies. Their interventions are mainly based on a personal attitude and informal guidance. There is no mention of systematic training on digital ethics, nor a clear framework of principles that guides the whole school. This creates a gap between intent and implementation. Although principals are concerned about issues such as the use of AI in the classroom or the substitution of the human role, they do not yet seem to have translated these concerns into concrete strategies. Thus, there is room for development at this level.

Based on the above, some directions for education policy emerge. First, it is necessary to create clear digital ethics policies that apply to all schools. These must cover issues such as the protection of personal data, the safe use of the internet and the responsible use of digital tools. Secondly, there is a need to introduce mandatory training for teachers and principals on digital ethics and ethics. This training should be continuous and focus on both practical issues and a critical understanding of digital challenges. Thirdly, it is proposed to develop material for pupils, with the aim of enhancing their digital responsibility. Fourth, it is important to strengthen participatory decision-making within the school, with the input of students, parents and teachers. In this way, rules and actions will emerge that meet the real needs of the school community. Finally, control and feedback mechanisms must be provided for the implementation of these policies to ensure their effectiveness and continuous improvement.

At the research level, there are opportunities for future study. The application of digital ethics policies in different school environments, urban and rural, primary and secondary, can be examined. It would also be helpful to explore students' views on the ethical issues of technology, as well as the extent to which they perceive the protection of their personal data. In addition, studies are needed to analyze how teachers experience digital ethics training and what factors reinforce or hinder it. Finally, it is worth investigating how the new questions that artificial intelligence and algorithms bring to education, from the point of view of the administration

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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